

Joaquin Barroso Flores

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Date of birth: March 15, 1978.

Position: Research Fellow at Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

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Education:

Bachelor of Sciences,

Masters and PhD from the National Autonomous University of Mexico

Current research: Excitonic transference mechanisms in photosynthetic systems; Design of unnatural nucleotides for the expansion of the genetic alphabet; Design of molecular recognition agents through the calculation of weak intermolecular interactions.

Published papers: 40

Hobbies: Reading; cooking; passionate baseball fan.

1.) What do you consider your greatest achievement?

Thanks to my *blog on computational chemistry* I've been fortunate enough to get in touch with fantastic people from around the globe during the last ten years. Pretty cool research collaborations have stemmed from those online interactions but more importantly some nice friendships have emerged. It is also always nice and uplifting to hear people say, particularly young students, at conferences that my blog has helped them finding solutions to their problems.

2.) How do you celebrate success?

Regardless of what we could consider success is, I believe success is hardly a personal effort but rather an achievement from collaboration. So, each time an achievement is made in our lab we celebrate together by going out for drinks; more often than not we do more than spending a good time: we also set the plan for future work in a relaxed environment – we always carry notebooks to these meetings.

3.) What was your worst nightmare?

I'm not sure, I've always considered myself very pragmatic so if one plan doesn't work there's always other paths to be taken. Nightmares –seem to me– are the result of avoidance or reluctance to change.

4.) What makes you lose track of time?

Pretty much anything, I still struggle from time to time to focus on a single task and sometimes I end up biting more than I can chew. However, thanks to my group we always succeed in managing most if not all the workload in time and above the expectations of our collaborators, but the credit is all theirs.

5.) What is the best advice you've ever given?

“Life is a travel. Enjoy the view.”

6.) What's the worst advice you've ever given?

“Don't worry, there's plenty of time.”

7.) What was the most unusual experience of your career?

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When I came back to Mexico to work at UNAM I was assigned to a new venue with developing infrastructure; there'd be times we didn't even have any electricity! It was very hard to work under such conditions.

8.) What's your favorite food?

That's a tough one. I enjoy all kinds of food but I guess Mexican in general is my favorite.

9.) What are your favorite pieces of music?

My taste in music has changed a lot over the years, ranging from classic rock to the most abstract forms of jazz and good old country music. I guess the only constant throughout the years have been the Beatles. Many times I've played the album "Bringing Down the Horse" by The Wallflowers on loop for hours.

10.) What was the most significant scientific advance in the last century?

Quantum mechanics, without a doubt. The establishment of the physics of the microscopic world unknowingly allowed ultimately for the technology, understanding and rational manipulation of molecules which in turn opened new research avenues ranging from materials to genetics. It also established the notion of discrete particles, namely atoms, in physics which at the time was largely debated philosophically by positivists.

11.) Do you have a favorite saying?

"Just do it"

12.) What is the biggest problem that scientists face today?

The speed with which disinformation is spread creates a distrust in science and hinders the development and implementation of science-based solutions to global problems. The anti-science movement that is a hallmark of our times has found notorious advocates in the limelight while gaslighting the work of millions of scientists. As I keep saying: it is quicker to watch a YouTube video with a conspiracy theory and call yourself 'woke' than just reading –let alone understand– a science book; the worst part is people calling the former practice 'doing research!' All this makes scientific communication from our part a moral duty.

13.) What is your favorite piece of research?

The one I still haven't made.

14.) Do you have a favorite place on earth?

Cluj-Napoca in Romania and Budapest in Hungary are places I know pretty well and love dearly, but as for places go, my absolute favorite one is my house.

15.) what was your most exciting discovery?

That is really hard! Each paper conveys a small discovery in a sense and that is exciting in itself. Finding out your hunch about macromolecular structure based on the monomers' structures was right, is exciting; finding that excitonic transfer mechanisms found in inorganic compounds is also found in photosynthesis, is exciting. We do these things for our enjoyment so its all fun.

16) Why did you choose chemistry?

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By the time I had to choose I found it a bit mysterious. Physics and Math seemed more sequential to me, whereas chemistry seemed less systematic at the time, I guess the syllabus was to blame and not my teachers: too much nomenclature, little reactivity..

17) If you weren't a scientist, what would you be?

Since I couldn't possibly be a professional baseball player, I would've liked being a baseball sportscaster. Studying architecture would've been cool too..

18) What is your secret / or not-so-secret passion?

Baseball. To some extent, during an important period of my life, world cinema was a passion of mine.

19) Do you notice a difference in computational chemistry research now and at the beginning of your career?

I've been doing computational chemistry for 20 years now and I've seen improvements in software, computation facilities and methods. I started working with Gaussian98 under the supervision of Prof. Juan A. Cogordan in Mexico City and we were tackling large molecules with Tin and Tellurium atoms back then, today they're a breeze.

20) What is the secret to publishing high-impact articles?

I wish I knew! Still, I think there are a few good pointers to suffer less during the publishing process: Language: Keep it simple but accurate, those of us who aren't native English speakers are in disadvantage so we need to always improve our language skills or join forces with someone proficient in English. For better or worse, English is the current official language of science.

Narrative: Your manuscript must be clear as to what was going on before your paper and what comes after; it doesn't have to be paradigm-shifting but if it's too disconnected from other research chances are you sound wild. Know your audience, sometimes I find many papers about a topic in a specific set of journals and whenever I find another paper from the same topic in a completely different journal I wonder if the authors did their homework about knowing where this conversation is being carried out.

I think of scientific research as a large ongoing conversation, so to be part of the conversation you must listen first. The work of a researcher begins and ends with the literature. People who just want to publish in top rated journals don't even read them! That's like trying to jump into a conversation with a random fact, only by chance you might be considered.

Finally, just do it. Fixing a bad paper is easier than fixing a non-existing one.

21) Could you list the 5 most important articles of your career?

This was the first major paper from my research group and one that cemented an ongoing collaboration with my good friend, Dr. Rodrigo Galindo at the University of Utah.

R. Galindo-Murillo, M. E. Sandoval-Salinas and J. Barroso-Flores, In Silico Design of Monomolecular Drug Carriers for the Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor Drug Imatinib Based on Calix- and Thiacalix[n]arene Host Molecules: A DFT and Molecular Dynamics Study, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, **2014**, *10*, 825–834.

When reading all the notoriety the non-cannonical base pairs from the Romesberg group raised, I had the feeling they would distort the double helix and thus they would be hardly useful in a practical sense. Rodrigo's excellent simulations proved us right.

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R. Galindo-Murillo and J. Barroso-Flores, Structural and dynamical instability of DNA caused by high occurrence of d5SICS and dNaM unnatural nucleotides, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **2017**, *19*, 10571–10580.

This was my first paper during my PhD in which I worked simultaneously in the wet lab as well as performing the computations with the mentors who cemented my knowledge in chemistry. We developed the Local Bond Order (LBO), an equation I should revise one of these days.

J. Barroso-Flores, R. Cea-Olivares, R. a. Toscano and J. a. Cogordan, Synthesis of the anisobidentate compound bis(2-amino-cyclopent-1-ene-carbodithioate)diethyltin (IV). Experimental and theoretical study, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, **2004**, *689*, 2096–2102.

This was the fruit of a collaboration that began online through my blog with the group of Chad Mirkin at Northwestern. Having collaborated with such an important group and published at an important journal is very cool, knowing it has been cited by two Nobel Laureates has been cooler.

J. Mendez-Arroyo, J. Barroso-Flores, A. M. Lifschitz, A. a. Sarjeant, C. L. Stern and C. a. Mirkin, A Multi-State, Allosterically-Regulated Molecular Receptor With Switchable Selectivity, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2014**, *136*, 10340–10348.

The last one opened a new avenue of research thanks to the curiosity of a student. The field of sigma holes is fascinating and knowing you can control reactivity at a synthetic level through such a seemingly abstract concept was a lot of fun.

G. Caballero-García, M. Romero-Ortega and J. Barroso-Flores, Reactivity of electrophilic chlorine atoms due to σ -holes: A mechanistic assessment of the chemical reduction of a trichloromethyl group by sulfur nucleophiles, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **2016**, *18*, 27300–27307.

22) What advice would you give to young people who decides to be a chemist?

Develop as many skills as possible during your earlier years, even if they seem disconnected from chemistry or even science. Learn how to program, learn to speak a new language, attend seminars on other topics, notice all the dots, make them yours, only then you may one day connect them and ultimately turn data into knowledge.